

Component-Based Finite Element Method for Flush Endplate Connections in Fire

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ABSTRACT

The fire design of bolted joints plays an important role in structural fire engineering. Therefore, this paper presents a numerical study on the modeling of flush endplate connections using the component-based finite element method in fire. The component-based finite element models of flush endplate connections are developed and validated against experimental results in terms of load-rotation curves, resistance, and failure modes in fire. The CBFEM is the combination of the component method and the finite element method. The results showed that CBFEM is an accurate model for the design of bolted steel connections in fire. The 5% plastic limit strain is set to predict the resistance of steel plates in fire.

Keywords: flush endplate connections, fire, component-based finite elements method, numerical design calculation

1 INTRODUCTION

The failure of steel connections can lead to the collapse of the whole building in fire due to their influence on the internal force distribution and overall deformation. Therefore, the resistance of steel connections in fire should be accurately predicted to understand the fire performance of the structure. The Cardington fire experiments were conducted to investigate the effect of connections on the mechanical behavior of steel structures at elevated temperatures (1). Flush end plate connections are commonly used in steel structures due to their ease of fabrication, good performance, and low cost (2). The elastic and plastic deformations of the connection components, including the end plate in bending, the bolts in tension, the column flange bending and the column web in shear, determine the nonlinear behavior of the flush end plate connections (3). EN 1993-1-8:2006 (4) standardizes the component-based method for the analysis of steel connections at ambient temperatures. The component-based method can be used to predict the fire behavior of steel connections using the reduction factors for structural steel, bolts and welds proposed in EN 1993-1-2:2005 (5).

Several numerical models (6-9) have been generated to model the flush endplate joints at elevated temperatures. Al-Jabri et al. (6) generated a finite element model using three-dimensional solid elements to study the response of flush endplate bare-steel connections and to determine the moment-rotation characteristics of the connections under the combined loading of a concentrated force at elevated temperatures. Tran (9) developed a model to predict the moment-rotation-temperature relationship of semi-rigid cruciform flush endplate connections in fire. Numerical models can be classified as numerical simulation (NS) and numerical design calculation (NDC). NS is an advanced numerical model that can use the measured material properties, geometric imperfections, and residual stresses to match the real mechanical behavior of structural members. The numerical models mentioned in this section are good examples of NS. However, the generation of a validated NS is not a feasible method at the fire design level due to the high computational cost. The NDC uses design material models such as a bilinear material curve with von Mises yield criterion, standard safety

factors, and a reduced number of finite elements and nodes compared to an NS. These simplifications can reduce the computational effort and make the model more practical at the design level. The CBFEM model is a special type of NDC for the design of steel connections at ambient and elevated temperatures. Figure 1 shows the material model for steel used in NS. Validation and verification are important steps to ensure the accuracy and reliability of a finite element model. Der et al. (10, 11) validated and verified the CBFEM to predict the fire resistance and failure modes of bolted lap joints and T-joints at elevated temperatures.

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

2.1 Test Description

In order to understand the mechanical response of flush endplate connections at high temperatures, the study by Yu et al. (12) on bolted beam-to-column connections was selected because several failure modes were observed. The connection consists of a UC254x89 column and a UB305x165x40 beam. In all tests, the steel column and beam were made of S355 and S275, respectively. A typical end plate connection was designed with three rows of bolts in accordance with UK design recommendations (13). The 325 mm deep x 200 mm wide flush S275 grade endplates were connected to the beams with M20 grade 8.8 bolts. Specimens were tested under steady-state conditions. The heating procedure for tested specimens is well described in the study (14). 20 thermocouples were installed in various locations around the connection to investigate the temperature distribution over the connection, It is stated that the recorded temperature values may be assumed as uniform (14). Specimen properties are presented in Fig. 1. The plate thickness used in the tests is 10 mm. The load is applied to the specimens through a special connector at an angle described in

Table 1. The specimens were loaded at three different angles of 35, 45, and 55° at room temperature, 450°C, 550°C, and 650°C. The test specimens used to validate the CBFEM model contain three rows of bolts, as shown in Fig. 1. At 20 and 450°C, the specimens with three rows of bolts and 10 mm plate thickness failed due to end plate fracture. At 550°C and 650°C, bolt failure was observed with very ductile behavior.

Fig. 1. The geometry of the test specimen (12)

Table 1. Lists of the test specimens (12)

Test Specimen	Plate thickness [mm]	Number of rows	Temperature [°C]	Nominal Load Angle [°]
Test 2	10	3	450	35
Test 3	10	3	550	35
Test 4	10	3	650	35
Test 6	10	3	450	45
Test 7	10	3	550	45
Test 8	10	3	650	45
Test 9	10	3	20	55
Test 10	10	3	450	55
Test 11	10	3	550	55
Test 12	10	3	650	55

2.2 Failure Modes

The authors of the experimental study reported that the specimens with 10 mm plate thickness failed due to two failure modes (12). Fracture of the end plate dominates the failure mode of the test specimens at ambient and 450°C. However, the bolts in the top row also have significant deformation, but no fracture is observed at 450°C, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Deformed shape of the connection at 450°C

At 550°C and 650°C, the top two bolts broke completely with high ductile behavior and moderate bending deformation occurred in the end plate. Fig. 3 shows the endplate and bolts at 650°C after failure.

Fig. 3. Deformed shape of the connection at 650°C

3 CBFEM

Two numerical methods described in prEN 1993-1-14:2022 (15) are numerical simulation and numerical design. In this study, the flush end plate connections are analyzed by numerical design calculation using CBFEM. CBFEM is a method for analyzing and designing connections of steel structures. It is a combination of the component method and the finite element method. The stresses, strains, and internal forces are calculated using the advantages of the finite element method to check the individual components according to the design specifications (4,5).

3.1 Material Models and Element Types

In numerical simulations, the material properties from the coupon test are generally used to simulate the behavior of steel connections. However, the NDC models use simplified material curves based on the design specifications. The CBFEM models the plates with elastic-plastic material with a nominal yield plateau slope $\tan^{-1}(E/1000)$ according to EN 1993-1-5:2005 (16). The von Mises yield criterion governs the response of the material under load. It is assumed to exhibit elastic behavior until it reaches the design yield strength f_{yd} . EN 1993-1-5:2005 recommends the value of 5% plastic limit strain to simulate the behavior of plates. Fig. 4 Displays the theoretical true and engineering stress-strain curves as well as the material model used in the CBFEM model.

Fig. 4. Material models used in FEM

3.2 Mesh Sensitivity Study

To assess the accuracy of the numerical design calculations and to optimize the computational cost, a sensitivity study of the mesh is carried out. The study shows that the coarse mesh predicts higher resistance than the fine mesh. Fig. 5 shows the influence of the number of elements on the connection resistance. However, increasing the number of mesh elements results in higher computational costs. Therefore, the optimized number of elements is chosen as 30 to subdivide the plates in CBFEM.

Fig. 5. Mesh Sensitivity Study

3.3 Validation

This chapter presents the validation of the CBFEM model using experimental results based on the requirements described by Wald et al. (17). The CBFEM model is validated in terms of load-deformation curves and failure modes. Heat transfer analysis was not performed during the numerical study since the recorded temperature values indicated uniform temperature distribution over the connection. Therefore, the connection model is subjected to the targeted temperature. The material properties of connection components were degraded by the relevant temperature degree.

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 6. The load-rotation graph a) 35°; b) 45°; c) 55°

Fig. 7. Deformed shape of the connection in CBFEM a) 450°; b) 650°

Fig. 6 shows the comparison between the load-rotation curves obtained from the experimental study (solid lines) and the CBFEM (dashed lines) for different load angles. Mostly, the CBFEM models developed load-deformation curves up to 2°. The experimental studies showed that the resistance decreases significantly with increasing temperature. The load angle also has an inverse effect on the connection resistance at elevated temperatures. At 35°, the load capacity of the flush end plate connections is underestimated by the CBFEM. The load-rotation response curves of the joint are in good agreement with the tests and the CBFEM model. In addition, there is a strong correlation between the initial stiffness derived from the CBFEM analysis and the results obtained from the tests. Fig. 7a indicates that a small crack develops during the tests and the plastic strain on the beam web near the weld is equal to the limit strain, as shown in Fig. 2. Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů.b shows the endplate and bolts at 650°C after failure and the plastic strain distribution on the specimen obtained from the CBFEM. As observed in the test, the CBFEM measures only 0.3% plastic strain while the bolts in the top row reach their ultimate capacity.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The CBFEM model was created to develop a numerical design calculation for flush end plate connections at elevated temperatures. The CBFEM model is validated using test results from the literature. The experimental and numerical plots show that the NDC models can predict the bolted joint behavior at both ambient and elevated temperatures. The developed CBFEM model can evaluate the mechanical response of flush end plate connections subjected to various loading conditions at elevated temperatures. The recommended 5% plastic limit strain for steel plates can also be used for fire design of steel connections.

This work was supported by SGS22/144/OHK1/3T/11. The authors are grateful for the funding.

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